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**WATER QUALITY VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT ON MAGSUNGAY RIVER:
INDUSTRIAL AND HOUSEHOLD WASTEWATER MANAGEMENT IN BACOLOD
CITY, NEGROS OCCIDENTAL**

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03 October 2022

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ACCEPTANCE PAGE

This Special Problem titled **“WATER QUALITY VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT ON MAGSUNGAY RIVER: INDUSTRIAL AND HOUSEHOLD WASTEWATER MANAGEMENT IN BACOLOD CITY, NEGROS OCCIDENTAL”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

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(Date)

DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The Special Problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface.
- II. Due acknowledgement has been made in the text to all other material used.
- III. The Special Problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Nicolle John B. De La Cruz', is written over a horizontal line. The signature is stylized and cursive.

NICOLLE JOHN B. DE LA CRUZ

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ABSTRACT

Freshwater is essential for both natural and human systems to survive. Clean water is a vital determinant of environmental health as well as a need for humans in terms of hygiene and health (Kim, J.-S., et al, 2019). According to Brook, N., (2005), Shift and variability in flow, emissions, population growth, competition for water, data availability and quality, and information gaps all contribute to the vulnerability of water management systems. This case study aims on assessing the vulnerability of Magsungay River as one of the main rivers of the city and cope it with the anthropologic situation of fragmentation in Bacolod City. The records show the trend of population growth in Bacolod City with 429,076 in 2000, 561,900 in 2015, and 624,783 in 2021. Also, expected population would take around in 2022 would be around 636,500 people, which indicates a linear growth towards population in the past two decades. According to the present LULC classifications of Bacolod City, the Built-up matrix covered 4846.86 hectares or 65%. Patches of Built-up settlements followed at 2115.18 hectares or 28% and patches of Bare soil at 267.75 hectares or 3% which is the same with clouds was 193.14 hectares or 3%. The water body areas were measured at 45 hectares or covering 1% of the land mass is the least area covered in Bacolod City. On Water Quality on Upstream area of Magsungay River, the result shows that the pH has a neutral state with 8.2 versus the range of 6.5-9.0. Temperature was ambient as required by standard. True color does not reach to maximum requirement with 15 CU. Dissolve Oxygen with 5 mg/L or ppm and Total Suspended Solids (TSS) is 13mg/L. Unfortunately, Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) has an off-standard result with 16mg/L or ppm versus 7mg/L specification from DAO 2016-08, while downstream result shows that the pH has a neutral state

with 7.1 versus the range of 6.5-9.0. Temperature was ambient as required by standard. True color does not reach to maximum requirement with 15 CU. Dissolve Oxygen with 5 mg/L or ppm and Total Suspended Solids (TSS) is 73mg/L. In downstream result on BOD is contrast with the upstream with 5mg/L versus 7mg/L standard. Based on the results, the waters of Magsungay river are greatly polluted due high density of population in Bacolod City with 624,783 numbers in 2021 covering 65% of Bacolod City's land use and land cover to residential or built-ups. This signifies how dense the city's population creating a devastating result on the water quality of Magsungay river. Even though, other quality parameters met the DAO-2016- 08 standards, unfortunately, the upstream area of the river contains high concentration of BOD which creates unvaried results towards ecological stability and sustainability.

Keywords: Bacolod City, LULC, Population, Water Quality, BOD, Vulnerability

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Freshwater is essential for both natural and human systems to survive. Clean water is a vital determinant of environmental health as well as a need for humans in terms of hygiene and health (Kim, J.-S., et al, 2019). The endpoint method is one way to evaluate vulnerability. It is the measurement of a certain feature of the water supply at a specific location's exposure to the full range of environmental stresses.

While sensitivity, adaptive capability, and vulnerability are useful integrative and multidimensional concepts for assessing the state of a water management system, they are also dynamic concepts that cannot be measured or observed directly.

The incorporation of landscape fragmentation as a methodology used to link pattern to process seemed to develop naturally from this first set of research papers. In this issue we chose to concentrate on the development and inclusion of landscape fragmentation in LUCC studies (Nagendra, H., et al, 2004). Over the past decade, research on the human dimensions of global change has clearly demonstrated that social uncertainties dominate over biophysical uncertainties in their impact on future environmental scenarios (NRC, 1999).

Landscape fragmentation results from patchwork conversion and development of sites, e.g., into settlements or other intensively used areas, and from linkage of these sites via linear infrastructure (Harris 1984, p. 4; Saunders et al. 1991; Forman 1995). LULC changes, illegal activities of multiple organizations in various development projects, road construction, the development of various infrastructures, the establishment of industrial spaces, and overexploitation of mines are just a few of the factors that have contributed to the growing habitat fragmentation in these areas

(Sobhani, P., et al, 2021).

According to Hamouda, M. A. (2009), in different parts of the world, several studies on vulnerability / sustainability assessment, creation of vulnerability / sustainability metrics, and mitigation and intervention assessment have either been completed or are currently underway. These practices and research projects are typically multidisciplinary in nature and are starting to provide a better image of global change vulnerability.

It has been difficult to compare research on a global scale due to the ‘fuzzy’ aspect of what vulnerability means and trying to understand what it is supposed to measure. Anthropogenic fragmentation of landscapes is known as a major reason for the loss of species in industrialized countries. Landscape fragmentation caused by roads, railway lines, extension of settlement areas, etc., further enhances the dispersion of pollutants and acoustic emissions and affects local climatic conditions, water balance, scenery, and land use (Jaeger, J. A. G., 2000). The effects of this fragmentation go beyond a simple reduction of the amount of habitat available. The process of breaking up existing habitat into disconnected pieces automatically involves a reduction in the habitat area (Beaudry, F. 2017).

Bacolod City, situated on the northwestern part of the island of Negros, is bounded by the Guimaras Strait on the west, the municipality of Talisay on the north, the municipality of Murcia on the east, and Bago City on the South. The City has land area of 162.67 square. In 1970, it had a population of 187,300. It has a cool invigorating climate with abundant rainfall. Most of the people speak Hiligaynon and the rest speak Cebuano (cited in HyBrain, 2018). Magsungay River (Magsungay River) is a stream (class H – Hydrographic) in Bacolod, Philippines (Asia) with the region font code of Asia/Pacific. It is located at an elevation of 49 meters above sea

level (Getmap.net, n.d.). As we view the cities perspective the researcher's aims of collectively see the changes and mitigation of the uprising crisis of Magsungay River.

Objectives of the Study

This case study aims to assess the vulnerability of Magsungay River as one of the main rivers of the city, and cope it with the anthropologic situation such as community infrastructures and solid waste management in the current views of fragmentation in Bacolod City with the following objectives:

To assess the vulnerability to contamination, depletion, and potential future problems of water quality of Magsungay River in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental,

1. To describe the potential vulnerabilities to Magsugay River in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental, including the likelihood of each vulnerability to happen and the potential consequences if not mitigated,
2. To develop environmental protection strategies, contingencies, and mitigation measures in partnership with the concerned Wastewater facility owners and Homeowners towards the long-term protection and sustainability of rivers and creeks in Bacolod City.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Vulnerability Assessment

It is necessary to review indices and indicators of vulnerability developed by previous authors to design a tool that can identify the degree of vulnerability of water management systems. There are a variety of national level indicators or collections of indicators that are useful in vulnerability studies. Some of these have been developed as general indices of human health, economic well-being, or development status, while others have been developed to address vulnerability directly (Hamouda, M. A., et al, 2009).

According to Brook, N., (2005), shift and variability in flow, emissions, population growth, competition for water, data availability and quality, and information gaps all contribute to the vulnerability of water management systems.

Hydro-physical and Ecological Vulnerability

The hydro-physical and Ecological Vulnerability is the most directly linked cause of water resource insecurity. A water management system is a dynamic system that is affected by a variety of factors, including population, economic growth, and social development (Wu, G., 2013). It is believed that integrated studies should come before cooperative development programs in rivers to improve program planning. Through a scenario analysis, this work seeks to give such a study regarding the vulnerability of water resource systems.

Water Quality

The problem of surface water contamination has been identified as one of the most pressing issues in developing countries. Most rivers in developing- world cities are the destination for effluents discharged by factories (Suthar, S., 2009). pH, turbidity, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), total alkalinity (TA), total hardness (TH), calcium hardness, chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), dissolved oxygen (DO), sulfate (SO₄), nitrate (NO₃), and chloride (Cl) were measured in water samples using the APHA method (1998).

According to Meriam Dictionary, pH is number on a scale with a value of 7 representing neutrality and lower numbers indicating increasing acidity and higher numbers indicating increasing alkalinity, used to determine the acidity and alkalinity of a solution. At a given temperature and time, BOD measures the amount of dissolved oxygen (DO) required by aerobic organisms to decompose the organic material present in each water sample. The amount of DO require for the decomposition of organic matter and the oxidation of inorganic chemicals like ammonia and nitrite is measured by COD (Rajput, K., 2021). A high level of water quality is implied by the absence of contaminants and the presence of nutrients and oxygen, two necessary elements. A common way to define water quality is to look at its chemical, physical, and biological makeup.

Landscape Fragmentation

Landscape or habitat fragmentation is the breaking up of a habitat or vegetation type into smaller, disconnected sections. It is generally a consequence of land use: agricultural activities, road building, and housing development all break up existing habitat (Beaudry, F. 2017). Habitat fragmentation is often defined as a process during which “a large expanse of habitat is transformed into a number of smaller patches of smaller total area, isolated from each other by a matrix of habitats unlike the original” (Wilcove et al. 1986). The literature on effects of habitat fragmentation on biodiversity is huge. It is also very diverse, with different authors measuring fragmentation in different ways and, consequently, drawing different conclusions regarding both the magnitude and direction of its effects (Fahrig, L. 2003). Mac Nally et al. (2000) found consistent vegetation differences between fragments and reference sites and concluded that apparent effects of fragmentation on birds could be due to preexisting habitat differences between the two landscapes. The definition of habitat fragmentation above implies four effects of the process of fragmentation on habitat pattern: (a) reduction in habitat amount, (b) increase in number of habitat patches, (c) decrease in sizes of habitat patches, and (d) increase in isolation of patches (Fahrig, L. 2003).

On average, the fragmentation studies that we reviewed were also poorly controlled. Only 42% of experiments included controls in which the same dependent variables were measured in the absence of the experimental perturbation.

However, on a positive note, 0.75% of landscape and patch–landscape experiments included controls. Also, local interview may help in determining the changes of the fragmentation in the area. The spatial scale of fragmentation studies imposes severe limits on the patterns observed and the processes involved. For

patch studies, spatial scale is simply the size of the experimental patches (McGarigal, K., & Cushman, S. A. 2002).

Habitat fragmentation has two major consequences: populations become more isolated and are reduced in size. Small compared with large populations have increased extinction risks because of natural catastrophes and environmental, demographic, or genetic stochasticity (drift). Genetic drift reduces the genetic variability of isolated populations and can result in strong genetic differentiation between populations. Most previous habitat fragmentation studies focused on rare and endangered species, which often consisted of only a few hundred reproductive individuals (Lienert, J. 2004). Mathematical models predict that such small populations will not be able to survive in medium time scales. However, also far larger populations with negative or variable long-term growth rates may ultimately face extinction (Holsinger, 2000). With an increasing loss and disintegration of habitat, the area of the remaining fragments diminishes, and the interpatch distance grows. The effect of this change in habitat distribution may be twofold: local populations become smaller and interpatch dispersal gradually decreases down to (almost) zero. Both effects lower the probability of an average habitat patch being occupied by a local population. Populations may become extinct purely by coincidence of demographic processes, or by a combination of environmental disturbance and stochastic demographic processes (Goodman, 1987; Leigh, 1981; Verboom et al, 1993, this volume).

If the fragmentation process becomes stabilized, the meta population may reach an equilibrium in the average number of occupied patches. This regional equilibrium contrasts with a lack of equilibrium on the local scale (May R.M, 1990). The time to reach equilibrium, the response time of the metapopulation to a

landscape change, will depend on the average rates of local extinction and recolonization (Opdam, 1990, 1991).

Vulnerability Assessment using Geographic Information System (GIS)

According to Bankoff, (2003), Vulnerability is multifaceted (physical, social, economic, environmental, institutional, and human), complex (changes over time), scale based (from individuals to countries), and site specific. The danger of climate change, threats, and human activity all play a role in determining how fragile a landscape is both internally and externally (Kanwar, Kuniyal, & Kumar, 2017). Taken from Jamwal, A., (2019), the main tools used to highlight the vulnerability through a digital map and index were the geographic information system (GIS) and remote sensing. Finally, during the field visit, all indicators' impacts were reported and observed, with one impact being assigned a value of "1" and no impact being assigned a value of "0." Based on parameter characteristics, the landscape vulnerability area is also explained.

Finally, in terms of comprehensive vulnerability, value means (x) were taken, and hazards vulnerability and high value of indicator classes were identified. Land-use and land-cover change (LULC) are also thought to be a major influence on mass movement. Hazards (landslides, floods, anthropogenic activities, and earthquakes) had a high impact intensity.

Because the ratio of barren and forestland was very low, the LULC status has a significant impact on large flood catchment areas of rivers.

Water Risk Assessment Method

Based on Xiao. Z, et al, (2019), this method of analysis can be used to examine the industrial sources of water risk in other nations and regions. Risk industries are industrial sectors that have a significant impact on river valley water risks. The following four types of industrial sectors fall under the category of water risk sources: High-risk industries are those that have a high level of water pollution and a high level of dependence on water resources; Water consumption industries are the industrial sectors with a relatively low level of water pollution but a relatively high level of dependence on water resources; Pollution industries are the industrial sectors with a relatively low dependence on water resources and a relatively high level of water pollution; Low-risk industrial sectors are those with a low level of water pollution and a low degree of dependence on water resources.

III. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

Lorem ipsum et dolor.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Study Area

This case study was explored within the context of landscape dynamics identified in the Magsungay River, Bacolod City, Negros Occidental. Site validation was from Nov – Dec 2021. Farmers and residents of commercial areas were interviewed regarding on the changes in the city's landscapes. Bacolod City, Negros Occidental's highly urbanized capital, contact, commerce, and service hub, and one of the twin provinces of Negros Island in the Visayan Islands cluster in the heart of the Philippine Archipelago. The cities of Talisay and Victorias border Bacolod on the northwest, Silay and Victorias on the northeast, the town of Murcia on the east and southwest, the City of Bago on the southwest, and the Guimaras Strait on the west. The total land area, except straits and bodies of water, is 16,270 hectares (162.67 km²) (HYBrain Development Corporation, 2018). Data were by Lamudi, the Philippines' premier real estate platform, indicated that since the first semester of 2016, there had been an increasing trend among property seekers looking for potential homes in Bacolod all the way to the second semester of 2018.

Figure 1. Bacolod City coverage area.

Source: <https://philnews.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/bacolod-city.jpg>

Figure 2. 2021 LandSat view of Bacolod City.

Source: <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>

Water Quality

According to DENR-EMB (Region 6), Magsungay River is classified as type C and based on DAO 2016-08, Class C freshwater rivers are classified to be used for agricultural, irrigation, livestock watering. Also, this type of river system can be used for engagement in fishing and fish propagation. The table below presents the DENR-EMB parameters for water quality for Type C waters based on DAO 2016-08.

Table 1

Water Quality for Primary Parameters on Type C Waters

Parameter	Unit	Water Body Classification Type C
BOD	mg/L	7
Chloride	mg/L	350
Color	TCU	75
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	mg/L	5
Fecal Coliform	MPN/100mL	200
Nitrated as NO ₃ -N	mg/L	7
pH (Range)	-	6.5-9.0
Phosphate	mg/L	0.5
Temperature	OC	25-31
Total Suspended Solids (TSS)	mg/L	80

Source: https://emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/DAO-2016-08_WATER-QUALITY-GUIDELINES-AND-GENERAL-EFFLUENT-STANDARDS.pdf

According to DAO 2016-08, All parameter standards above (Table 1) shall be always enforced and complied with, to maintain the quality of water bodies based on their intended beneficial uses. Primary parameters are the required minimum water quality parameters for each water body to be monitored.

Conceptual Framework

→ **Conceptual Framework**

INPUTS	PROCESS	OUTPUTS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site Information • DENR Consultation • Community Interviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Base Map Preparation • Sample Testing and Analysis • Water Quality Assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vulnerability Assessment • Environmental protection strategies, contingencies

Literature Search

Data was based on the available information and compliances from Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR-EMB-R6) and Bacolod City Government on the sites of wastewater facilities standard and household index in Bacolod City. Data culled by Lamudi, the Philippines’ premier real estate platform, indicated that since the first semester of 2016, there had been an increasing trend among property seekers looking for potential homes in Bacolod all the way to the second semester of 2018.

Figure 3. Data of houses built in the Bacolod City as of 2017.

Source: <http://www.bacolodcity.gov.ph/files/Upated-Socio-Economic-Profile-2017.pdf>

Table 2*Number of infrastructures in Bacolod City as of 2017*

Unit	Number of Infrastructures
Residential	784
Commercial	242
Industrial	7
Institutional	17
Others	2
Total	1,127

Source: <http://www.bacolodcity.gov.ph/files/Upated-Socio-Economic-Profile-2017.pdf>**Table 3***Length of roadway in Bacolod City as of 2017*

Unit	Length of Roadway (km)
Concrete	241
Asphalt	9
Gravel	58
Unpaved	0.1564
Total	309

Source: <http://www.bacolodcity.gov.ph/files/Upated-Socio-Economic-Profile-2017.pdf>

Unlike other cities such as Vigan, Bacolod's constructions gone enormously in recreational and commercial buildings. With the increase of population in Bacolod City, the distortion on the city's landscape also increases. This also validated the land-use of Bacolod City changes as population increases.

Table 4

Population of Bacolod City in 2000 – 2021

Year	Total Population Enumerated in Various Censuses
2000	429,076
2015	561,900
2021	624,783

Sources: (1) <https://psa.gov.ph/sites/default/files/Bacolod%20city.pdf>
(2) <http://population.city/philippines/bacolod/>
(3) <https://worldpopulationreview.com/world-cities/bacolod-population>

Figure 4. Population trend in Bacolod City.

Source: <https://worldpopulationreview.com/world-cities/bacolod-population>

The records show the trend of population growth in Bacolod City with 429,076 in 2000, 561,900 in 2015, and 624,783 in 2021. Also, expected population would take around in 2022 would be around 636,500 people, which indicates a linear growth towards population in the past two decades.

Base Map Preparation

Topographic maps and other relevant maps from the literature research were scanned, digitized and geo-referenced to Geographic Coordinates-Negros Occidental or World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS 84 Datum). Digital line graphs of contours, roads, rivers, and relevant features were created and organized using Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques. A base map was generated from shapefile created.

Using Landsat 4-5 Thematic Mapper (TM) C1-Level1 dated April 7, 1994, and Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI)/Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) C1-Level1 dated April 28, 2019 in the acquisition of the LandSat Image with the aid of US Geological Survey's (USGS) Earth Explorer. This data was used due to it has a clearer view of Bacolod City.

After the image acquisition, pre-processing using QGIS 3.10.0 A Coruña was conducted, the collected Landsat data were pre-processed using the semiautomatic classification plugin (SCP). A shapefile containing the political boundary information of Bacolod City. Both the Landsat bands and shapefile were used during the clipping of raster and vector files. Conversion of clipped bands into surface reflectance using the same plugin.

There were five (5) delineated Land-used and land cover macro classes (MID):

1. Water which includes all areas of open water and lakes;
2. Vegetation which includes areas covered by trees, planted sugarcane fields and other agricultural crops;
3. Built-up areas which include areas characterized by high and low settlements and infrastructures and other lands disturbed by development or human intervention.

4. Bare Soil which includes harvested sugarcane fields, rock, and gravel.
5. Clouds which are the spaces that captured upon gathering the clearest data that was downloaded on the LandSat.

Figure 5. Geographic Information System image of Bacolod City, Negros Occidental cited January 2021 showing massive fragmentation of built ups on the city.

Sample Gathering and Site Visit

On September 19, 2021, site visit was conducted in Magsungay River near Brgy. Mansilingan, Bacolod City. Around 9:00am to 11:00 am, with the aid of local residence, the identification, classification, inventory and map major land use and potential sources of contamination and pollution were conducted. Water sampling of at least two (2) water samples were undertaken from deepwells located upstream and downstream of the of residential and industrial areas.

Plate 1: Downstream area of Magsungay River.

Plate 2: Upstream of Magsungay River.

Plate 3: Water sampling and site visit.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Land Use and Land Cover

The image of Bacolod City shows that less land is covered with green lands and most of it are covered in red which are commercial and residential areas. As the vegetation area decreases and the Land-used for Built-ups increases.

Using the QGIS 3.10.0, the data gathered from LecoS, evaluated, and tabulated with graphical representation.

Table 5

Land Cover and Land Used Data gathered from LecoS

Classification	Land Cover		Landscape Proportion
	m2	ha	
Water	450000	45	0.006
Vegetation	21151800	2115.18	0.283
Baresoil	2677500	267.75	0.036
Build-ups	48468600	4846.86	0.649
Clouds	1931400	193.14	0.026

Figure 6. Pie graph data using excel to show the land use and land cover of Bacolod City.

According to the present LULC classifications of Bacolod City, the Built-up matrix covered 4846.86 hectares or 65%. Patches of Built-up settlements followed at 2115.18 hectares or 28% and patches of Bare soil at 267.75 hectares or 3% which is the same with clouds was 193.14 hectares or 3%. The water body areas were measured at 45 hectares or covering 1% of the land mass is the least area covered in Bacolod City.

With the given data and observation, that the built up already provided large spaces on the area as the population increases, demands of shelters and infrastructures are needed to suffice the necessity of the people. Although with great built-up show on the area, the effects of it are truly massive in water quality of primary rivers especially Magsungay River.

Water Quality Assessment

Through water quality analysis, determination of vulnerable areas was done. A minimum of two (2) water samples from (Magsungay River) in Bacolod City, at least two (2) water samples from riverbanks located upstream and downstream of an industrial wastewater facility was collected and sent to the laboratory for chemical and microbiological analyses. Laboratory analysis interpretation of river water samples was done DENR-EMB for compliance and standard reference. Table 6 below showed the results of the laboratory analysis.

Table 6*Physico-Chemical Results of Water Sample in Upstream*

Parameter	Results	Units	DAO 2016-08 (Class C)	Method
pH	8.2	-	6.5-9.0	Electrometric
Temperature	25	0C	25-30	Laboratory
Color (True)	15	CU	75	Visual Comparison
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	5	mg/L	5 min.	Iodometric
Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD)	16	mg/L	7	5-day BOD Test
Total Suspended Solid (TSS)	13	mg/L	80	Gravimetric (dried @ 103- 105 0C)

Source: Appendix A Results of Water Sample in Upstream

The results showed that the water has a pH of 8.2 (neutral state) when put against the acceptable range set by DAO of between 6.5 and 9.0). Temperature was ambient as required by the DAO standard. True color did not reach the maximum requirement of DAO with 15 CU. Dissolved oxygen was at 5 mg/L or ppm and Total Suspended Solids (TSS) is 13mg/L. Unfortunately, the Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) test has an off- standard result with 16mg/L or ppm as compared to the acceptable 7mg/L specification from DAO 2016-08.

The implication of high BOD is the presence of high organic matter in the river signifies high pollution as the dissolved oxygen present in the river water is being consumed by microorganisms such as bacteria where aquatic animals such as fish are prone to receive less oxygen. Another contributor to the high level is the presence of nitrates and phosphates, which are components of fertilizers, human wastes, and even industrial wastes. The high level of BOD may be favorable towards invasive species such as leeches, catfish and sludge worms that promote imbalance and threat towards the ecosystem of Magsungay River.

Table 7*Physico-Chemical Results of Water Sample in Downstream*

Parameter	Results	Units	DAO 2016-08 (Class C)	Method
pH	7.1	-	6.5-9.0	Electrometric
Temperature	25	0C	25-30	Laboratory
Color (True)	15	CU	75	Visual Comparison
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	5	mg/L	5 min.	Iodometric
Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD)	5	mg/L	7	5-day BOD Test
Total Suspended Solid (TSS)	73	mg/L	80	Gravimetric (dried @ 103- 105 0C)

Source: Appendix B Result of Water Sample in Downstream

The results show that the downstream water sample has a pH of 7.1, which is within the DAO standard range of 6.5-9.0. Temperature was ambient as required by standard. True color did not reach the maximum requirement with only 15 CU. Dissolved oxygen was at 5 mg/L or ppm and the Total Suspended Solids (TSS) is 73mg/L. In contrast to the upstream water samples with higher values than the DAO standard, the downstream result on BOD is lower than the standard at 5 mg/l.

The amount of biological oxygen demand in streams and rivers is affected by dissolved oxygen. Water pH, temperature, microorganisms, and organic and inorganic materials all influence the rate of oxygen consumption. Another contributor of change in BOD is the presence of small streams that are connected to the body of Magsungay River which provide water volume to the river.

Vulnerability to Contamination Assessment

The potential sources of surface and subsurface pollution were systematically identified, their potential hazard to the water source classified, and their spatial

distribution mapped. The vulnerability of the rivers and creeks to contamination was assessed based on the integrity of the well structures and existing onsite and offsite potential sources of contamination. The areas for immediate risk mitigation were identified and the conceptual aquifer protection strategies were developed. Contamination on the water quality was drawn through tables to determine most vulnerable areas with high percentage of contaminant and off-standard water quality (i.e., pH, Temp. BOD, TSS, DO).

Summary of Vulnerability

The identified major vulnerabilities of the Magsungay River water source are:

1. Tree-cutting/poaching, human and animal encroachments into the immediate surroundings and watershed area located in Magsungay River and community water sources.
2. Current unsanitary conditions around of Magsungay River and nearby community area.
3. Encroachment of human settlements, slash-and-burn farming and other undesirable land practices.
4. Elevated BOD values and microbiological contamination of water, which frequently occur even in calm-flowing current.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results, the waters of Magsungay River are greatly polluted due to high density of population of 624,783 in Bacolod City in 2021 with residential and built-ups areas covering 65% of land use and land cover of Bacolod City. This signifies how the city's dense population is creating a devastating result on the water quality of Magsungay River. Despite this, other quality parameters met the DAO-2016-08 standards. However, the upstream area of the river contains high concentration of BOD which creates potential effects of contamination and deterioration towards ecological stability and sustainability. Several vulnerabilities to contaminations are found that possibly may weaken the ecological growth and sanitation of the river for its industrial and commercial use.

The researcher, went through possible routes of mitigation through Water Resource Protection Plan, which provides several outputs on the classification and desire on maintaining the cleanliness and usability of Magsungay River. Also, to add mitigations on water conservation and wildlife protection to avoid, possible threat such as massive soil erosions, biological chemical contamination, invasive species, and wildlife imbalance.

Water Resource Protection Plan

A Source Water Protection Plan was developed based on the findings of the Magsungay River study, identifying major water resource vulnerabilities, and developing mitigation/remedial strategies to ensure the river's long-term protection and sustainability.

Tree-cutting/Poaching, Human and Animal Encroachments into the Immediate Surroundings and Watershed Area located in Magsungay River and Community Water Sources

The issue is the introduction of potential microbiological and chemical contamination into the river and streams; and possible destabilization of riverbanks that may lead into increased surface run-off, soil erosion, water pollution and worst, water poisoning. During the site visit, tree- poaching/cutting near riverbanks and the presence of a carabao (water buffalo) and other domestic animals such as dogs and cats was observed about 500 m in the river water sources.

The objective is to rehabilitate, protect, conserve, and manage the watershed area river water sources; and to protect them from destructive anthropogenic activities and potential sources of microbiological and chemical contamination. Some mitigation measures are:

1. Reforest denuded areas of the riverbanks.
2. Conduct information and education campaign (IEC) and advocacy in the community on the importance of Magsungay River and proper sanitary practices around river water sources. Employ/involve the locals in the tree planting and growing or reforestation projects.
3. Barangay/LGU Personnel should continue conducting the 2x (twice-a-week) a week ground inspection of the riverbanks of Magsungay River.

Current Unsanitary Conditions around of Magsungay River and Nearby Community Area

The problem is that the Magsungay River's potential microbiological and chemical contamination problems are caused by unsanitary conditions around the

river; the underlying aquifer is porous and permeable, allowing contaminants to naturally travel from surface to subsurface; in fact, nearby community source water is already contaminated with Coliform, E.Coli, and Fecal Streptococcus. The WRPP's goal is to prevent the gradual entry of potential contaminants into the Magsungay River because of poor sanitary conditions in the surrounding area. This can be addressed thru the following actions.

1. Maintain the practice of removing, relocating or managing potential sources of contamination within the following delineated protection zones: 50m-radius microbiological protection zone where potential sources of microbiological contamination such as septic tanks, latrines, decaying organic matter, animal/human pathways, etc., are removed, relocated to more than 50m away, or managed (thru engineering mitigation measures) to prevent them from contaminating the river; and 200 m-radius chemical protection zone where potential sources of chemical pollutants such as oil, fuel and grease spillages, machine and welding works, backwash fluids, water treating and bottle washing chemicals, etc., are removed, relocated further away from the river, or are managed thru engineering mitigation measures;
2. Conduct regular cleaning and sanitation within the river area;
3. Properly inform and educate the community that their river water source is already contaminated and that it requires immediate cleaning and disinfection to prevent the growth and spread of microbial contamination; and
4. LGUs coordinate with the surrounding communities on proper sanitation around.

Encroachment of Human Settlements, Slash-and-Burn Farming and Other Undesirable Land Practices

If not addressed, the above vulnerability could lead to increased erosion, siltation, and contaminant load, as well as the eventual extinction or loss of wildlife. The WRPP's goal is to help/advocate for the rehabilitation, protection, and preservation of the Magsungay River to ensure the river's water sources' long-term viability. Some mitigation measures are:

1. Assist/advocate in the rehabilitation and protection of the Magsungay River as a whole;
2. Advocate/assist in tree-growing in the denuded areas of the river; and
3. Try to have a representation and/or attend meetings of the Department of Environment and Natural Resources – Environmental Management Bureau (DENR-EMB R6), which is the policy and decision-making body.

Elevated BOD Values and Microbiological Contamination of Water, which frequently occurs even in calm-flowing current.

The objective is to put up an effective multi-barrier water treatment system taking into consideration future developments near the river and at the same time maintaining the original microbiological purity and chemical composition of the natural water. More specific objectives are to experiment, search for and implement an economically feasible testing method that could help monitor, mitigate, and evaluate BOD concentration on upstream and downstream. Some mitigation measures are:

1. Continue the plan to install coagulation system or flocculation system on industries to remove substantial organic components that increase the BOD concentration and promotes other environmental complications.

2. Study the feasibility urban planning near water resources and provide with local LGUs to confirm possible rise of BOD concentration and invasive species.
3. Try to convince management of industries to reduce the strict 7mg/L standard as required by DAO 2016-08 of DENR-EMB R6.

Policies and Regulations

The Environmental Management Bureau (EMB), under the Department of Environment and Natural Resources' jurisdiction, is the primary national government agency in charge of water resource management in the Philippines (DENR) in terms of quality standards and requirements.

The EMB oversees administering and enforcing the Philippine Clean Water Act (Republic Act No. 9275) of 2004, which mandates comprehensive water quality management among other things. Its responsibilities include, but are not limited to, the creation of water quality management areas and management boards to protect, restore, and revitalize the quality of surface water and groundwater resources; issuance of water pollution or wastewater discharge permits, and collection of appropriate fees based on pollutant/contaminant load; preparation and implementation of water quality guidelines; and review and setting of effluent standards every five years.

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doi:10.1016/j.eiar.2019.106285

APPENDICES

Appendix A Water Quality Results – Upstream

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CAN : C21-10-56-10C
Date of Issue : 10/7/2021
RAN : R21-09-171C
INVOICE # : --
Date Received: 9/21/2021
Date Sampled: --
Date Analyzed: 9/21-27/2021

CERTIFICATE OF ANALYSIS

Sample Description	Parameters	Results	Units	DAO 2016-08 Water Quality Guidelines (Class C)	Methods
Upstream (211) Date Sampled: September 19, 2021	pH	8.2	--	6.5-9.0	Electrometric
	Temperature	25	°C	25-30 ^{max}	Laboratory
	Color (True)	15	CU	75	Visual Comparison
	Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	5	mg/L	5 min.	Iodometric
	Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD)	16	mg/L	7	5-Day BOD Test
	Total Suspended Solids (TSS)	13	mg/L	80	Gravimetric (dried @ 103-105 °C)

Note : ^aThe natural background temperature as determined by EMB shall prevail if the temperature is lower or higher than the WQG; provided that the maximum increase is only up to 10 percent and that it will not cause any risk to human health and the environment.
The customer is given 7 days upon receipt to raise questions or clarifications on any part or content of the certificate, otherwise the result(s) is/are deemed accepted.

Total No. of Sample : 1 **Total Analysis :** 6

Sample Submission : Submitted by the Customer

Reference : Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater, 23rd ed.

Remarks : Results relate only to the item tested and received by the laboratory

Certified Correct by:

 SHEENA JOY C. CADELINA, RCh
 PRC No. 0011580
 Laboratory Head

Approved by:

 ALVIN P. BACOL, RCh
 PRC No. 0011788
 Vice President-Operations

Page 2 of 3

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RESULTS OF ANALYSIS

Sample Description	Parameters	Results	Units	DAO 2016-08 Water Quality Guidelines (Class C)	Methods
Upstream (211) Date Sampled: September 19, 2021	pH	8.2	--	6.5-9.0	Electrometric
	Temperature	25	°C	25-30 ^(b)	Laboratory
	Color (True)	15	CU	75	Visual Comparison
	Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	5	mg/L	5 min.	Iodometric
	Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD)	16	mg/L	7	5-Day BOD Test
	Total Suspended Solids (TSS)	13	mg/L	80	Gravimetric (dried @ 103-105 °C)

Note : ^bThe natural background temperature as determined by EMB shall prevail if the temperature is lower or higher than the WQG; provided that the maximum increase is only up to 10 percent and that it will not cause any risk to human health and the environment.
The customer is given 7 days upon receipt to raise questions or clarifications on any part or content of the certificate, otherwise the result(s) is/are deemed accepted.

Total No. of Sample : 1 **Total Analysis :** 6

Sample Submission : Submitted by the Customer

Reference : Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater, 23rd ed.

Remarks : Results relate only to the item tested and received by the laboratory

Appendix C

USGS Earth Explorer Database

Appendix D

DAO 2016-08 Water Quality Guidelines for Primary Water

Table 3. Water Quality Guidelines for Primary Parameters

Parameter	Unit	Water Body Classification									
		AA	A	B	C	D	SA	SB	SC	SD	
BOD	mg/L	1	3	5	7	15	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	
Chloride	mg/L	250	250	250	350	400	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	
Color	TCU	5	50	50	75	150	5	50	75	150	
Dissolved Oxygen ^(a) (Minimum)	mg/L	5	5	5	5	2	6	6	5	2	
Fecal Coliform	MPN/100mL	<1.1	<1.1	100	200	400	<1.1	100	200	400	
Nitrate as NO ₃ -N	mg/L	7	7	7	7	15	10	10	10	15	
pH (Range)		6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.0	6.0-9.0	7.0-8.5	7.0-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.0-9.0	
Phosphate	mg/L	<0.003	0.5	0.5	0.5	5	0.1	0.5	0.5	5	
Temperature ^(b)	°C	26-30	26-30	26-30	25-31	25-32	26-30	26-30	25-31	25-32	
Total Suspended Solids	mg/L	25	50	65	80	110	25	50	80	110	

Notes:

MPN/100mL – Most Probable Number per 100 milliliter

n/a – Not Applicable

TCU – True Color Unit

(a) Samples shall be taken from 9:00 AM to 4:00 PM.

(b) The natural background temperature as determined by EMB shall prevail if the temperature is lower or higher than the WQG; provided that the maximum increase is only up to 10 percent and that it will not cause any risk to human health and the environment.

Source: https://emb.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/DAO-2016-08_WATER-QUALITY-GUIDELINES-AND-GENERAL-EFFLUENT-STANDARDS.pdf

Appendix E

Quantum GIS (QGIS) program with Remote Sensing Technology

Source: <https://i.ytimg.com/vi/MhYz2xwZeq4/maxresdefault.jpg>

Appendix F Water Risk Assessment

		High degree of water pollution	Low degree of water pollution
High water consumption ↓ Low water consumption	High Risk Industrial sectors: with high water consumption and pollutant emission, bringing excessive pressure to water resources and water environment of the basin, the industrial sectors needs to be highly focused.	Water Consuming Industrial sectors: with low pollutant emission but a large water consumption, the industrial sectors carries a large consumption of water resources	
	Pollution industrial sectors: with low demand for water resources but serious pollutant emission	Low risk industrial sectors: the industrial sectors have low risk in basin water resources and water environment due to its low water consumption and pollutant emission.	

Source: Xiao, Z., Gao, J., & Su, Y. (2019). China's water risk assessment and industrial source analysis based on the localization of WWF water risk assessment tools. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 78, 106285. doi:10.1016/j.eiar.2019.106285